

Taxonomy of gesture-sound relationships in Manual Interactions with Imaginary Objects (MIO) in Hindustani Dhrupad vocal improvisation

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Abstract

Over the years, multiple taxonomies have emerged to categorize the diverse range of movements, particularly those linked to music, with a wealth of literature in music performance exploring this topic. Despite extensive discussions, conflicting opinions persist, and a consensus on a single taxonomy remains elusive, highlighting the intricate nature of movement types. In Hindustani (North Indian Classical) Dhrupad vocal music, singers often appear performing manual interactions with imaginary objects, referred to as "MIOs" (Manual Interactions with Imaginary Objects) in this study. This paper revisits existing taxonomies in respect to gesture-sound relationships, examining perspectives in classifying MIOs within these frameworks. Based on the results, it underscores the challenge of classifying MIOs into these established, emphasizing their unique status in the realm of music-related movements.

Keywords

Gesture-sound relationships, taxonomy, systematic musicology, Hindustani vocal music, ethnomusicology, embodied music cognition

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to all the musicians who have generously participated in my research over the years. The observations of their gestures have played a crucial role in shaping the content of this study. The work received no funding.

Introduction

Over the years, various taxonomies have been proposed to categorize the wide array of movement types, particularly those related to music. A rich body of literature on this subject exists within music performance, comprising edited books, volumes, and individual discussions. Despite the extensive exploration of the topic, conflicting opinions persist, and a unanimous consensus on a single taxonomy has yet to be reached, underscoring the complexity of movement types.

In the realm of Dhrupad vocal music, a sub-genre within Hindustani (North Indian Classical) music, during improvisation singers frequently engage in the simulation of manual interactions with imaginary objects, termed as "MIIOs" (Manual Interactions with Imaginary Objects) in this work. Specifically, despite the absence of a real, tangible object (Rahaim, 2013), vocalists appear to move as if they are stretching, pulling, pushing, or throwing something. These movements comprise gripping, main action and releasing phases and convey a sense of contending with or yielding to an imaginary resistive force, suggesting that distinctive patterns of acoustic features in the voice may correspond to the effortful interactions associated with the physical properties of imagined objects, such as viscosity, elasticity, weight, and friction. This paper aims to emphasize that MIIOs represent a unique category of music-related movement, making their classification and alignment within existing taxonomies challenging.

Literature Review

The term "gesture" holds diverse interpretations across various disciplines, encompassing cognitive sciences, experimental psychology, philosophy, linguistics, biomechanics, human-computer interaction, and musicology. Despite its widespread use, these interpretations often lack clarity. This section elucidates the current research context's application of the term and its involvement in examining relationships between gesture and sound, specifically in MIIOs.

Gesture

Traditionally, gesture was broadly defined as body movement conveying information (Kurtenbach & Halteen, 1990). More recently, this definition has expanded beyond physical movement to include sonic and imagistic aspects. Presently, gesture is conceptualized as both a mental and corporeal phenomenon (Leman & Godøy, 2010: 8), conveying expressive information and meaning. The term now encompasses a range of manifestations, from empty-handed movements to those involving real object manipulation, general body movements, dynamic auditory contours in music, visual imagery, feelings of motion (including kinaesthetic, tactile, proprioceptive sensations, and ideomotor responses), speech, and even experiences in touch, taste, and smell (Luciani, 2004).

Hatten (2004: 95) contends that musical gestures signify intrinsic musical qualities characterized by 'significant energetic shaping through time with unique expressive force.' Contrary to viewing melody as a sequence of specific pitches, music theorist Ernst Kurth (1922) conceptualizes its essence as arising from internal patterns of energetic tension and release. Kurth suggests that these patterns manifest in the acoustic realm as curves of musical intensification and abatement, resulting in a 'play of [psychological] tensions.' Musical experience is often perceived as a fluctuation of tension, giving rise to emotional responses (Lerdahl & Krumhansl, 2007; Krumhansl & Schenk, 1997; Vines et al., 2006).

These dynamic configurations of musical gestures can be depicted through physical hand movements. As per Godøy (2009: 205), the hands not only follow the geometric aspects of sound, such as pitch contours, pitch spread, rhythmic patterns, textures, and timbral features but also convey the sensations of effort embedded in the music. These termed 'motion bells' (Camurri et al., 2003) can be conceptualized as successive event units, their energy centered around moments of heightened emphasis. Psychologist Daniel Stern (2010) describes them as peaks and decays or impulses and rebounds, believed to have originated from our innate ability to navigate through approach and withdrawal. Stern (ibid.) regards these units as a dynamic

expression of 'vitality,' resulting from a combination of five elements: force, motion, time, space, and intentionality.

Despite recognizing variations in sensory modalities among individuals, adopting a singular, shared term offers the advantage of transcending the Cartesian divide between the physical and the mental, delving into the realm of embodied cognition. In the context of music, Jensenius et al. (2010) utilize this term to encompass the amalgamation of sensations arising from physical movement and sound. Similarly, Delalande (1988) points out that the term 'musical gesture' exists at the intersection of observable actions and mental representations.

While I endorse the idea of employing a unified term for gesture, for the sake of clarity, this paper adopts distinct terms for each modality:

- 'gesture' or 'physical gesture' is used to describe voluntary, goal-directed, and coherent movement units or chunks in music performance (even if they don't directly produce sound). These encompass a prefix, the (main) excitation phase, and a suffix (referred to as 'action' by Jensenius, 2007).
- 'melodic phrase' or 'melodic movement' is utilized for sound gestures (sonic event units).

Additionally, I will reserve the more general term 'movement' for discussions that broadly pertain to motion, specifically the displacement of a body part of the human skeleton. Additionally, I will retain the term 'action' for goal-oriented, coherent body movement units that may not necessarily be associated with music production.

Event units are perceived as outcomes influenced by a combination of music-related and biomechanical factors (Hogan and Sternad, 2007; Nelson, 1983), along with the body's motor-control dynamics and our attention and short-term memory capabilities (Snyder, 2000). The subjective experience of these event units is often dominated by dynamics, seen as being instigated and guided by some propelling force (Runeson & Frykholm, 1983; Stern, 2010), a phenomenon particularly prominent in instrumental excitatory movements.

Hand gestures in Hindustani singing

Hand movements serve various functions in both performance and teaching contexts, including expressing the performer's personal connection with musical sounds (Clayton, 2005; Rahaim, 2013; Leante, 2009; Fatone et al., 2011), communicating with fellow performers (Moran, 2007), and engaging with the audience (Clayton, 2007) or students (Pearson, 2013). Hindustani

singers, as observed by Rahaim (2009) and based on personal observations, appear to interact with melodic content in two primary ways: employing open hands or closed hands (forming an initial grip).

In the open-handed mode, hands trace curves effortlessly in space, creating a melographic representation of the sound, with the hand shape assumed to mirror the voice's timbre (Rahaim, 2013 and interview testimony). Conversely, the closed-handed mode involves hands forming a grip before seemingly manipulating an imaginary object with effort, acting against an envisioned opposing force associated with altering its shape, size, or orientation. For instance, gestures may resemble the singer moving an object like a ball around in space, bouncing it on the floor, creating the shape of a knot with both hands, or pulling a heavy object or stretching something like a rubber band (Fatone et al., 2011; Rahaim, 2013), as seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Snapshots of MIOs during vocal improvisation for (a) Afzal Hussain and (b) Lakhan Lal Sahu.

This paper specifically focuses on interactions involving closed hands and imaginary objects, such as pushing, pulling, or exerting force on a substantial object in space, as well as stretching and compressing an elastic material. When these gestures occur, the emphasis shifts from the hands themselves to the envisioned object, maintaining a connection with which the performer engages. It appears as though the body is temporarily extended through an interface to the real world, allowing individual notes to be perceived as graspable objects. It remains uncertain whether vocalists possess a vivid visual imagery of these objects as clearly defined geometrical constructions or if their mental imagery is limited to the proprioceptive sensation of physicality (an aspect that could be explored in future research). Nevertheless, in each instance, vocalists manipulate notes as if they were handling them like smooth pitch glides, holding, extending, and then releasing them. This contact persists as long as the object serves the purpose of vocalization, after which vocalists seem to unconsciously let it go. As outlined by Rahaim (2009: 82), in such interactions, the connection between gesture and voice appears to be rooted

in the consistent physicality of the imagined object held by the hands rather than its spatial and acoustic dimensions. While it is not expected for a performer to consciously compute real-time mathematical calculations of physical laws, it seems that prior recurring experiences are linked to the melodic activity during singing. Previous research work has revealed that when Dhrupad singers engage with an imaginary object, the relationship to the sound is embedded in the object's affordances (Rizzolatti & Sinigaglia, 2008: 34; Norman, 1988), i.e. the interaction possibilities that the object provides—determined by its physical properties such as viscosity, elasticity, weight, friction, etc.—and the perceived effort it entails.

Affordance in interaction design, a concept describing the practical opportunities a real object invites for the user (Rizzolatti & Sinigaglia, 2008: 34; Norman, 1988), plays a crucial role in this examination. Introduced by Gibson (1977; 1979) in ecological psychology, affordance refers to a set of potential motor actions evoked by the intrinsic properties of a real object. In essence, while various ways exist for an individual to interact with an object, these are constrained by its physical or geometrical properties and the surrounding context. This concept underscores the significance of prior sensorimotor experience, challenging the traditional cognitive theory's view that our understanding of a real object is solely based on its physical properties and its relation to other real objects. Instead, it emphasizes that our knowledge, termed action-based knowledge or know-how, is derived from the actions we have previously performed in connection with this type of real object. This perspective aligns with the fundamentals of enactive theories (O'Regan & Noë, 2001; Thompson & Varela, 2001; Varela et al., 1991) and ecological psychology by Gibson (1977; 1979).

Taxonomies and classifications

Instead of presenting an exhaustive list, only two taxonomies are discussed here. The first exclusively addresses movements accompanying singing, while the second pertains to general music-related movements. Notably, existing taxonomies for singing movements by scholars such as Clayton (2007, 2005) and Davidson (2005, 2001) do not necessarily encompass the classification of MIIOs. The second, more general movement taxonomy is elaborated upon to underscore the inherent ambiguity in classifying MIIOs.

1. Clayton's taxonomy (2007, 2005) specifically delves into the movements of vocalists in Khyāl singing, categorizing them based on their function in performance or teaching. Given the pronounced similarity between singing movements and speech movements, this taxonomy was crafted by employing a procedure analogous to McNeill's extension of 'Kendon's

continuum' (McNeill, 2005, 2000, 1992) and the research conducted by Ekman & Friesen (1972) in the study of speech movements. The taxonomy encompasses 'markers' denoting musical processes or structure, 'emblems' for communication with other musicians or the audience, and 'illustrators,' which are 'tied to the content of singing, appearing analogous to the melodic flow or "motion"' (Clayton, 2007: 75). Of particular interest to this work is only the last type, also referred to as 'gesticulations' by Kendon and McNeill.

2. Godøy et al. (2012) have formulated a widely acknowledged movement classification, wherein music-related movements are categorized according to their (a) content, (b) timescale, and (c) function.

(a) The content pertains to the performer's training level, sociocultural background, and performance practice (solo or ensemble) and does not hold particular significance for the present study.

(b) The timescale corresponds to the numerous temporal and structural intricacies inherent in movement, as considered in movement analysis methods (Francoise et al., 2012). This involves the subdivision of continuous body motion into smaller chunks characterized by varying timescales:

(b1) The micro-timescale refers to durations of 0-0.5 seconds for individual tones and stationary movement features, as defined by Cambouropoulos (2001);

(b2) The meso-timescale encompasses durations ranging from 0.5 to 5 seconds, referring to movement events (gestures) and the interaction between gestures and sonorous objects, as defined by Schaeffer (1966), Godøy (2006), Bonini & Rodà (2001), Mion (2003), and Hsieh & Luciani (2005);

(b3) The macro-timescale pertains to longer durations, encompassing entire sections or even entire works, as delineated by Camurri et al. (2005), Suzuki & Hashimoto (2004), Canazza et al. (2004), and Bresin & Friberg (2000).

Studying the relationships between movement and sound presents a challenge due to the need to comprehend information at various levels of detail (Godøy, 2009). The fundamental premise of the present research is that the most prominent connections between movement and sound are anticipated at the meso-level timescale (Godøy et al., 2016). At this level, coarticulation phenomena play a role in merging distinct gestures into more extensive movement units or trajectories, and conversely, in consolidating continuous streams of information into cohesive movement units or 'atoms,' which are meaningful entities, concrete motor images, trajectories, or Gestalts (Godøy, 2010; Buxton, 1986; Cox, 2006; Godøy et al., 2006a; Küssner, 2014;

Noyce et al., 2013). This concept is applicable to both sonorous and movement modalities and extends from Schaeffer's (1966) notion of the sonorous object to Godøy's (2006) concept of the gestural-sonorous object.

At the meso-level timescale, the focus in sound analysis revolves around patterns or events, including motives, ornaments, melodic shapes, and dynamic profiles (Schaeffer, 1952; Bregman, 1990), which 'may be primordial to the singular sound or tone' (Godøy, 2009: 209). Consequently, the analysis concentrates on movements typically spanning between 0.5-5 seconds, and this perspective has implications for the processes of annotation, segmentation, and feature extraction (Henbing & Leman, 2007).

(c) The function aspect delves into the purpose of movement in music performance and serves as the basis for our exploration of MIIOs. The functional categorization can be subdivided into communicative, sound-producing, ancillary, and sound-accompanying.

(c1) Communicative movements are designed for communication and can be further categorized into endogenous (within the performer), performer-performer, or performer-audience interactions (Jensenius, 2007). However, these are not relevant to the scope of this study.

(c2) Sound-producing movements encompass human actions that either generate (excitation gestures) or alter (modification gestures) the resonant characteristics of an instrument. These movements exhibit a distinct cause-and-effect relationship with the sound, dictated by physical laws and a precise energetic connection with the instrument. Excitation gestures involve initiating the sound, while modification gestures entail subsequent adjustments to it (Cadoz, 1988).

(c3) Ancillary movements (Jensenius, 2007; Wanderley & Depalle, 2004), also known as sound-facilitating movements (Jensenius et al., 2010), coincide with sound-producing movements but do not directly contribute to sound generation. Ancillary movements may encompass actions that performers undertake to enhance and convey expressiveness in a performance, such as articulating, dynamically shaping, and phrasing the sound. This category of movements has undergone extensive examination by Caramiaux et al. (2012), Nusseck & Wanderley (2009), Wanderley (2002), and Vines et al. (2004). Alternatively, ancillary movements may also refer to supportive actions that instrumental music performers employ to aid sound-producing movements in various ways, without being directly responsible for sound production. These movements primarily aim for physiological comfort, such as preventing fatigue and

avoiding strain injuries. This aspect has been studied, for example, by Dahl et al. (2010: 38) in the context of drumming gestures.

(c4) Sound-accompanying movements do not contribute to the direct production of sound but instead follow music, as seen in listening situations, dancing, or acting to music (Jensenius et al., 2010; Jensenius, 2007). Such movements may involve the approximate mimicry of the motor activity underlying a sound-producing gesture, referred to as 'motor mimicry' or 'motormimetic sketching' by Godøy et al. (2006b: 258). They can also encompass tracing some acoustic aspect that follows the evolution of a sounding (real) object's resonance, termed 'sound tracing' by Godøy et al. (2006a: 27). In the first case, it involves imitating the excitation gesture (the presumed cause) that might have produced the sound, while in the second case, it entails tracing features of the resulting sound (the effects of the action, i.e., images of how materials resonate). Rocchesso et al. (2015) and Caramiaux et al. (2014, 2011, 2010) argue that listeners tend to mimic the imagined sound-producing gesture when they can identify the sound source (the "causal" character of movement in relation to sound). In contrast, in "non-causal" situations, they resort to manually describing the sound. Further discussion on this topic is provided in the next section.

In practical terms, the delineation between the mentioned functional categories is not always straightforward, and distinctions are often challenging. This implies that a movement could potentially align equally well with multiple categories or be considered a combination of different classes. Jensenius (2007: 57) illustrates the relationship between movement and sound as a continuum in Figure 2, spanning from cases with close relationships to those with more loosely connected associations. While the four function classes are positioned on this continuum, movements in practice may fall in between any of these classes, highlighting a frequent ambiguity in terms of movement classification.

Figure 2. The 4 different music-related movement types (based on function) and their connection to sound on a continuum reflecting link to sound (Jensenius, 2007: 57).

It is worth noting that scholars from the research group that introduced the previously mentioned taxonomy have also recently employed an alternative classification (Godøy et al., 2016). This alternative taxonomy comprises three categories: (a) sound-producing, (b) sound-accompanying, and (c) amodal, affective, or emotive. The last category encompasses any type of movement, including the physical, sonic, and imaginary (motor-imagery), associated with global sensations of the sound. This involves concepts like images of effort, balance, and other elements commonly encountered in dance. While this category could indeed encompass MIIOs, the use of this alternative taxonomy underscores the complexity of developing a classification system that is comprehensive and capable of capturing the wide array of nuances in movement.

Examining the broader movement classification based on function, categorizing singing movements as sound-accompanying appears intuitive, given their role in adding expressivity and supporting vocalization (as mentioned in interviews). However, in the previously referenced taxonomy, the term has only been applied in conjunction with instrumental movements, making it inappropriate for use in the context of singing in this research. There seems to be some confusion in defining ancillary and sound-accompanying movements in terms of whether they must be linked to sound-producing movements or not. This ambiguity is evident in Delalande (1998) using the term 'accompanying gestures' for gestures accompanying sound-producing gestures, while Jensenius et al. (2010) use the term exclusively in response to music in a listening context. The variation in terminology highlights that research in music-related movements has predominantly focused on instrumental music making.

At this juncture, I contend that the ancillary type of movements in the aforementioned functional taxonomy should not be exclusively tied to sound-producing (instrumental) movements, as they can also be observed in vocal performance. For example, singers may employ movements to facilitate voice production (Brunkan, 2015) or for articulation and phrasing purposes (Pearson, 2016: 200). Therefore, I propose that sound-accompanying movements encompass all types of movements that do not directly produce sound, regardless of whether they pertain to producing or reacting to sound. In other words, I suggest defining a movement class called 'sound-accompanying' to include expressive, supporting, motor-mimetic, and sound-tracing movements as sub-categories accompanying movements that produce or respond to sound. In the following section, I will aim to assert that not only does the previously mentioned 'functional' taxonomy lack the ability to classify

singing movements, but also that MIOs should be regarded as a unique case, adding further complexity to their classification.

Ambiguity in classifying MIIOs

The functional classification mentioned earlier makes a clear separation between movements directly involved in sound production or enhancing expressiveness during music performance and those that respond to sound by either imitating sound-producing movements or tracing sound features. However, I contend that making such a functional distinction is not feasible or straightforward in the case of singing, particularly in the context of MIIOs. Classifying MIIOs solely as sound-producing movements poses challenges, and categorizing them as imitating sound-producing or sound-tracing movements also presents difficulties. I will now elaborate on the reasons behind this assertion.

The direct production of sounds pertains to instrumental (effective) movement, characterized by a strong energetic coupling between movement and sound governed by strict physical laws dictating how the sounding body vibrates in response to excitation. In the case of MIIOs, where no tangible object is involved, there is no evident energetic coupling between the hands and the imagined object, or at least it is not readily apparent. Although the performers' movements seem directed toward this imagined object, it is not the object itself that vibrates and produces the sound. Thus, labeling these movements as sound-producing gestures becomes challenging.

Simultaneously, there may be a direct or indirect physical impact on the mechanism of voice production. For example, a rapid downward push might induce a desirable wobbling effect in the voice (as in gamaks), or increased muscle tension in the arms could aid in controlling the diaphragm. However, there is certainly no direct energetic coupling between the hands and the supposed source of sound. Therefore, characterizing MIIOs as sound-producing movements may not be accurate. One could argue that MIIOs are better described as sound-accompanying movements that rely on imitation.

Godøy (2006b) distinguishes between the imitation of sound-producing gestures and sound-tracing gestures. However, it remains unclear whether the performer is engaging with the melody by mimicking gestures that could potentially produce these sounds or by tracing certain aspects of the voice. Despite the absence of a tangible object, the connection to the sound appears to be mediated by the imagined object. Consequently, it seems more plausible that the performer is not primarily interacting with the outcome of their movements (tracing the sound) but is primarily focused on gestures that could potentially produce the sound. There is an observable synchronization and temporal congruency between the voice and the apparent manipulative movements in terms of various features such as melody, dynamics, and timbre. Vocalists seem to draw upon prior sensorimotor experiences derived from recurrent patterns

and familiar interactions with the real world to execute these imitations. Fundamental embodied experiences like grasping, stretching, and releasing an elastic object serve as examples. However, the imagined object in use would not typically produce any sounds under normal conditions; an elastic band, for instance, is not expected to make a sound when stretched. Consequently, it is also not accurate to characterize these movements as imitating sound-producing gestures.

Similarly, Cox (2011) distinguishes between observed sound-producing gestures, analogous sound-producing gestures, and other analogous exertions when considering imagery. The first case involves imagining playing the violin while listening to a violin piece ('intra-modal MMI'), the second case pertains to imagining playing the same piece on a different instrument or singing it ('cross-modal MMI'), and the third case involves imagining the use of any other modality that is not primarily acoustic to match the pattern of the audio stimulus (also cross-modal MMI). Perhaps the third category by Cox (imagining the use of another modality to match the pattern of the audio stimulus) would be the most suitable way to classify MIIOs. However, this classification lacks the essence of MIIOs, which involves the mediation of movement by the imagined object and the imitation of effort as a means to simulate the imagined energy coupling between the hands and the object. Whether this energetic coupling can extend to include sound and to what extent this sound aligns with what the imagined object could potentially produce or the actual sound of the voice remains an open question.

Conclusion

The implied ambiguity suggests that it is unclear whether in MIIOs there exists a relationship between manual gestures and the voice and how robust this relationship is. Furthermore, it is uncertain whether this relationship, if present, can be detected by an observer. In essence, while MIIOs are rooted in recurrent patterns of our interaction with the environment, they are not necessarily grounded in learned sensorimotor contingencies. This implies that, although the object may be envisioned as producing the sound and the gesture may be envisioned as potentially sound-producing, the ultimate connection to the sound remains unclear. Further investigating this relationship calls for systematic empirical research work.

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